

ISic4370

A fragmentary gymnasial dedication to Hermes and Herakles

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2021-01-06 - Jonathan Prag amended bibliographic reference

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Found in 2017 in re-use in the wall of a modern house in the old centre of Centuripe

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

A fragmentary slab of local limestone, broken on all sides

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Remains of six lines of Greek letters, evenly spaced, all incomplete

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neatly cut, regular and evenly spaced letters without serifs. Broken-bar alpha; sigma with parallel top and bottom bars; omicron almost full size

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][Ἐρ]μαῖ Ἡρα[κλεῖ][---]
2. [---]νασιαρχ[---]
3. [---]ουτ[]υ[---]
4. [---]οντο[]α[---]
5. [---]εσκευαζ[---]
6. [---]α[---]

Apparatus

transcription by Jonathan Prag from photograph

γυμνασιαρχοῦντος or γυμνασιαρχήσας or γυμνασιαρχησαντος
παρεσκευαζεν?

Translation

Commentary

Discovered summer 2017 and reported on online blog sites, with images. See <https://archeosicilia.blogspot.co.uk/2017/09/centuripe-scoperta-la-dedica-di-un.html> [<https://archeosicilia.blogspot.co.uk/2017/09/centuripe-scoperta-la-dedica-di-un.html>] (Isabella di Bartolo, 18 September 2017). The traces in line 1 suggest a dedication to Hermes and Herakles; line 2 appears to be a reference to the office of gymnasiarch; lines 3 and 4 presumably contain the name(s) of the gymnasiarch(s). Line 5 is perhaps a reference to the motivation for the dedication.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

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Photo from <https://archeosicilia.blogspot.co.uk/2017/09/centuripe-scoperta-la-dedica-di-un.html>